

Moving Forward with the Windows on the Universe Center for Astronomy Outreach

Josie Fenske & Lars Lindberg Christensen (NSF's NOIRLab)

Arizona's signature desert air and wide-open skies make it a state with a large, astronomy-interested resident community as well as a destination of choice for national and international travelers interested in exploring the night sky. From casual tourists to science enthusiasts to advanced amateur astronomers, the region offers an abundance of night-sky wonders and discovery for all levels of knowledge. In the summer of 2024, a new attraction will be added to the list of must-see Arizona locations: the [Windows on the](#)

[Universe Center for Astronomy Outreach](#), or Windows Center for short, will open in the retired McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope (McMath-Pierce), located at Kitt Peak National Observatory (KPNO), a Program of NSF's NOIRLab. It will be operated as a part of the Kitt Peak Visitor Center (KPVC), which was established in 1964.

For many years, the McMath-Pierce was the largest solar telescope in the world. Equipped with three heliostats, the

Figure 1: The recently retired McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope located at Kitt Peak National Observatory, soon to host the Windows on the Universe Center for Astronomy Outreach. Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/P. Hordálek (Institute of Physics in Opava)

reflecting solar telescope was used to study the structure of sunspots and to obtain solar spectra. The telescope was decommissioned in 2017, but the approximately 8000-square-foot interior has been given a new life through funding from the National Science Foundation (NSF) as the future home of a dynamic astronomy visualization and presentation center focused on astronomy.

The McMath-Pierce's unique environment and its rich history of scientific discovery make for an experience that combines a historical retrospective of the facility with an overview of modern astronomy. By exploring the interactive exhibits and educational programs offered in the Windows Center, visitors will gain a deeper understanding of the history of astronomy research and how it has led to humanity's current understanding of the cosmos. The Sun will also play an integral role in the Windows Center exhibits and content with solar themes woven throughout as visitors experience the iconic McMath-Pierce architecture and participate in unique live daytime solar disk viewing, interactive spectroscopy, and nighttime viewing of celestial showpieces.

All Windows Center programs and exhibits are designed to enhance participants' knowledge and perspective of science and will be presented in visitors' predominant languages: English, Spanish, and O'odham. Staff will have training in both content and presentation skills to deeply connect with and engage visitors. Rather than just delivering facts, staff will tell stories and offer views that are challenging, honest, and provocative — all the while appreciating the responsibility of communicating at and about a national research institution. Through effective communication by exhibits and staff,

History of the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope

The concept of a national optical observatory was born at a conference at Lowell Observatory in Arizona in 1953 as ideas were developing to strengthen science in the United States. A few years later, in 1957, around the time of the launch of the Soviet Sputnik satellite, civil engineer William F. Zabriskie was commissioned to prepare three preliminary designs for a solar telescope building. Following Zabriskie's preliminary design work, the Association of Universities for Research in Astronomy (AURA) contracted with the Chicago engineering firm of Skidmore, Owings, & Merrill, which developed 10 designs, 2 of which were recommended for final consideration. The striking building design was constructed in 1962 using designs by American architect Myron Goldsmith and Bangladeshi-American structural engineer Fazlur Rahman Khan.

The Arizona Sky Islands — part of a collection of isolated mountain ranges that stretch from southeastern Arizona to northern Mexico — proved to be a favorable location for a new solar telescope, given their high altitude and relatively isolated "ecozone" in the midst of the Sonoran Desert. Kitt Peak, whose original O'odham name is Iolkam Du'ag, is located on the ancestral lands of the Tohono O'odham. A lease was signed in 1958 with the Tohono O'odham Nation, formerly known as the Papago Tribe of Southern Arizona, that allowed construction of Kitt Peak National Observatory. This national observatory became the home to a large collection of optical, infrared, and radio telescopes, with a rich legacy of discovery and pioneering advancement in technology. The solar telescope — now called the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope after solar astronomers Robert Reynolds McMath and A. Keith Pierce — was opened in 1962 for scientists and technicians to perform observations and develop instruments. Astronauts from the Mercury, Gemini, Apollo, Skylab, and even Space Shuttle missions used the telescope's 1.5-, 1.6-, and 2.1-meter heliostat mirrors during the 1960s and 1970s for their unique capability to project large-scale images of the Moon.

Now that the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope has finished its science mission, it is being transformed into an outreach center.

Figure 2: 1964 view of several of the Apollo astronauts in the Control Room of the McMath-Pierce. Left to right: Astronaut Donn Eisele, Don Wilhelms (USGS), Spencer Titley (UA), Ray Zedekar (NASA), Astronaut Theodore Freeman, Astronaut Frank Borman, Astronaut Eugene Cernan, and Harold Masursky (USGS). Credit: USGS

Figure 3: Locations of exhibit areas in the Windows Center main level. Credit: KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA

the Windows Center has the potential to positively influence life outcomes, particularly for young people, by illuminating career possibilities and providing motivation to obtain advanced education.

All content developed for the planetarium and exhibition will be shared with other established science centers and museums around the globe, creating international impact and visibility. The Windows Center will be one of only a few facilities in the world with free, openly accessible materials for other science centers.

Windows Center Spaces

Building modifications are currently underway, and once they are completed, the individual spaces within the facility will be filled in phases. Phase I includes a revamped front entrance, the first iteration of the Lobby area, a fully revamped Control Room, first-iteration exhibits throughout the rest of the space, and a Science On a Sphere (SOS) data visualization system. Visitors can expect an experience built on NOIRLab's foundational principle of Discovering Our Universe Together.

Entrance

The visitor experience begins at the original entrance to the telescope's main floor. The old glass storefront design has been completely replaced

and developed into a more energy-efficient and secure facade. The shade structure will be constructed from colored glass, creating ever-evolving rainbow shadows that change depending on the Sun's location throughout the day. The placements and colors of the glass blocks are inspired by the spectrum of our Sun, created using the very spectrometer that still lives in the Control Room. Benches near the entrance will allow for rest, interaction, and snack breaks.

Lobby

The Lobby establishes a sense of place for visitors, orienting them to the telescope by providing an overview of some of the accomplishments of astronomers who have used the facility over the years. Displays describe the mission and priorities of NSF and its role in astronomy research, in funding the construction and operation of the McMath-Pierce as an observatory, and in funding the development of the Windows Center. The Lobby also serves as the gathering place for arriving groups or individuals and the location for volunteers and staff to welcome and orient visitors. Near the Lobby, large,

aesthetically pleasing wall graphics serve as photo opportunities for visitors.

A primary focus of the Lobby area is KPNO's location on the lands of the Tohono O'odham Nation, specifically on Iolkam Du'ag (the original O'odham name for the mountain), as well as the relationship between the observatory and Nation members. The Windows Center makes it a high priority to foster partnerships with Nation members both in the development of content and in O'odham staff working as interpretive guides to the space. Working with Tohono O'odham staff members and representatives from the Himdag Ki: Hekihu, Hemu, Im B I-Ha'ap (the O'odham name for the Tohono O'odham Nation Cultural Center & Museum), content is being developed to provide visitors with an understanding of the O'odham culture and their important part in the history of KPNO. By implementing features such as a welcome message by a Tohono

O’odham tribal member, architecture reflecting the Tohono O’odham building styles, and a garden showcasing culturally important plants, the Windows Center recognizes the Nations history, their longstanding connection with the night sky, and the land they consider sacred.

Understanding Our Universe Exhibit Gallery

Visitor flow naturally progresses from the Lobby into the Understanding Our Universe Exhibit Gallery, which provides a blend of static and interactive exhibits covering modern astronomy and physics, the electromagnetic spectrum, and the instruments astronomers use to probe the Universe. In this area, visitors can better understand our place in the Universe, how we know what we know about the cosmos, and why that knowledge is relevant to visitors.

Beginning with a You Are Here display, visitors take a journey across the Universe starting in southern Arizona and moving progressively out from Earth, across the Solar System, through the Milky Way, and into the realm of the galaxies. Throughout the exhibit, the nature of planets, stars, nebulae, and other common and more exotic objects is explained. Next, to address the question of “How do we know?” the visitor is introduced to light and the electromagnetic spectrum to understand how nature transmits information across vast distances of space. Woven into the messages of each exhibit is the answer to the question “How does this relate to me?” By showcasing the personal stories of past and present scientists, the exhibits show relevance, applications to daily life, and the benefits gained by humanity from having a clear, in-depth understanding of how the Universe works.

Control Room

Beyond the Understanding our Universe Exhibit Gallery, visitors enter the Control Room. This room is where astronomers operated the heliostats and observed the Sun for decades, and several vintage aspects of the room have been preserved and incorporated into the experience. With its restored computers and analog control panel, the room evokes a sense of nostalgia. Here, during observing sessions with the three original heliostats, visitors can witness firsthand what the Sun looks like through a large solar telescope and learn to identify features like sunspots and granulation. The room also features a large live solar spectrum on a touch screen interactive panel so visitors can explore the details of the spectrum and identify the elements behind its absorption lines.

Astronomy Lab

As they exit the Control Room, visitors enter a gallery tentatively named Kitt Peak — I’itoi’s Garden, which features images and information about nature on the Sky Island and the Tohono O’odham Tribe’s culture and connection with the cosmos. Adjoining this gallery is the Astronomy Lab, which will be used for scheduled educational programs and multi-use events, especially those that engage students from the Tohono O’odham Nation.

Science On a Sphere Theater

At the far end of the exhibit area is the SOS Theater with an exhibit that projects myriad videos and images on a spherical multimedia screen where visitors, together with a guide, can virtually explore planetary data from our Solar System and beyond. Global phenomena and issues such as climate change will also be shared by using

Key Takeaways for Visitors

- We are all connected to the night sky.
- You too can be an astronomer through citizen astronomy.
- Light that we capture through our eyes and instruments tells us about our place in the Universe.
- Every tool we have developed was inspired by questions that astronomers wanted to answer.
- We are guests of the Tohono O’odham Nation and honor this special place.

Key Learning Objectives of the Windows Center

- Visitors will understand the context of the collaboration between KPNO and the Tohono O’odham Nation that allows astronomical facilities to operate at KPNO.
- Visitors will be inspired and awed by the Universe, our current understanding of it, and the role that the facilities at KPNO have played in conjunction with NSF’s astronomy facilities around the world.
- Visitors will appreciate the history of the McMath-Pierce and be transported back in time to experience the operation of the facility since the 1960s.
- Visitors will exit the Windows Center with a sense of the form and function of the McMath-Pierce through restored instruments and facilities that, wherever possible, will function as they did in the past to provide exceptional observations of the Sun and other objects in space.

compelling representations of real data and timely science. The focus of this exhibit is to provide visual context for understanding complex scientific concepts to give visitors a better understanding of modern astronomy and climate science.

Development Phases

With the completion of Phase I, the Windows Center will already be a place that evokes a sense of wonder for visitors, inspiring and encouraging them to pursue a deeper connection with the Universe.

NOIRLab can neither successfully complete the Windows Center exhibits nor run the KPVC operations without supporting funding beyond that provided by visitors. Membership programs, events, naming sponsorships,

endowments, and fundraising campaigns are all strategies that NOIRLab will pursue to obtain needed funds.

With the execution of subsequent phases — as funds allow — the Windows Center experience will be further enhanced with a facility-wide audio system, outdoor exhibits, and a gallery inside the hulking metal tower of the McMath-Pierce where visitors will be able to enter the facility’s optical viewing tunnel and learn how sunlight is collected by the telescope. Interactive exhibits and a planetarium adjacent to the lobby will allow visitors to immerse themselves in the cosmos as revealed by KPNO and NSF observatories around the world. Planetarium shows will include voyages across space, recountings of significant moments of discovery, and virtual tours of NOIRLab

sites, giving visitors a better sense of how contemporary astronomy impacts humanity’s understanding of the Universe. The digital planetarium comes with an extraordinary 3D astronomical database, projection system, and well-designed user interface.

The unique experience offered by the Windows on the Universe Center for Astronomy Outreach will leave visitors with an expanded understanding of the history of astronomy research and how it has led to our modern view of the cosmos. With a probing look into the physical wonders of the Universe, set against a backdrop of the McMath-Pierce Solar Telescope facility’s history of scientific achievement, visitors will be inspired to continue their journey of discovery beyond their visit to the Tohono O’odham Nation and Kitt Peak National Observatory.